

ILM-FAN MUAMMOLARI TADQIQOTCHILAR TALQINIDA

ILM | TA'LIM | INNOVATSIYA | MAKTAB
YANGI O'ZBEKISTON | BUYUK KELAJAK
UCHINCHI RENESSANS

ANIQ
FANLAR

TABIY
FANLAR

TIBBIYOT
FANLARI

TEXNIKA
FANLARI

IJTIMOYIY-GUMANITAR
FANLAR

PEDAGOGIKA
VA PSIXOLOGIYA

KONFERENSIYA QATNASHCHILARI:

- ✓ TALABALAR
- ✓ MAGISTRANTLAR
- ✓ DOKTORANTLAR
- ✓ YOSH OLIMLAR
- ✓ O'QITUVCHILAR

KONFERENSIYA YO'NALISHLARI:

- 🌱 Aniq fanlar
- 🌿 Tabiiy fanlar
- 🏥 Tibbiyot fanlari
- ⚙️ Texnika fanlari
- 👥 Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar
- 🎨 San'at va madaniyat fanlari
- 🏃 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport
- ✍️ Filologiya fanlari
- 📖 Pedagogika fanlari
- 🧠 Psixologiya fanlari

UCHINCHI RENESSANS

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INTEGRATED REDUCTIVE LEACHING OF ZINC CAKE AND RECOVERY OF ZINC CHLORIDE IN HYDRAZINE–HCl MEDIA

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Abstract: This study investigates the reductive leaching of zinc cake using a hydrazine-hydrochloric acid system. The obtained zinc chloride solution was purified by neutralization with zinc oxide-bearing technogenic materials and cementation using zinc dross. The purified solution was concentrated by reverse osmosis filtration, and zinc chloride was successfully obtained from the saturated solution.

Keywords: zinc cake, hydrazine, hydrochloric acid, zinc chloride, cementation, reverse osmosis, zinc extraction.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda rux kekini gidrazin-xlorid kislota tizimida tiklovchi tanlab eritish jarayoni o‘rganildi. Olingan rux xlorid eritmasi rux oksidi saqlagan texnogen materiallar bilan neytrallanib, rux droslari yordamida sementatsion tozalandi. Tozalangan eritma teskari osmotik filtratsiya orqali to‘yintirilib, undan rux xloridi ajratib olindi.

Kalit so‘zlar: rux keki, gidrazin, xlorid kislota, rux xloridi, sementatsiya, teskari osmos, rux ajralishi.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследован процесс селективного восстановительного выщелачивания цинкового кека в системе гидразин-соляная кислота. Полученный раствор хлорида цинка очищался нейтрализацией техногенными материалами, содержащими оксид цинка, и цементацией с использованием цинковых дрессов. Очищенный раствор концентрировали методом обратного осмоса с последующим получением хлорида цинка из насыщенного раствора.

Ключевые слова: цинковый кек, гидразин, соляная кислота, хлорид цинка, цементация, обратный осмос, извлечение цинка.

Problem Statement. Zinc cake contains a considerable amount of zinc together with impurity metals such as iron, copper, cadmium, and lead [1]. Conventional processing methods often provide low selectivity and high reagent consumption. Therefore, developing an efficient method for selective zinc extraction and purification of zinc chloride solution is an important task [2].

Research Methodology. Zinc cake was leached using a hydrazine–hydrochloric acid solution under controlled conditions. After filtration, the obtained zinc chloride solution was partially neutralized with zinc oxide-containing technogenic materials and purified by cementation using zinc dross. The purified solution was then concentrated using reverse osmosis filtration to obtain saturated zinc chloride solution [3].

Obtained Results. The hydrazine-assisted chloride system provided effective dissolution of zinc-bearing phases and improved zinc transfer into solution. Cementation with zinc dross successfully removed impurity metal ions from the electrolyte. Reverse osmosis filtration allowed efficient concentration of the purified zinc chloride solution and subsequent production of zinc chloride crystals.

Scientific Conclusion. The study showed that hydrazine-assisted hydrochloric acid leaching is an effective method for selective zinc extraction from zinc cake. Hydrazine improved the decomposition of stable zinc-bearing phases and increased zinc transfer into solution, while cementation with zinc dross effectively removed impurity metals from the zinc chloride electrolyte.

Reverse osmosis filtration allowed efficient concentration of the purified solution with lower energy consumption. As a result, purified zinc chloride was successfully obtained from technogenic zinc-containing residues, demonstrating the potential of the proposed resource-saving hydrometallurgical process.

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